

Identifying Business Objectives

Purpose: To identify the organizational context, processes, problems, and opportunities that can be solved with machine learning (ML) solutions in research, development, and innovation (RDI) projects.

The stakeholders involved in completing this artifact and identifying problems for RDI projects are: Business Owner (BO), Domain Expert (ED) and Data Scientist (CD)

Business objective 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none">develop innovative and intelligent solutions for monitoring and controlling flying insects BO	Justifications 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none">to minimize the risks of contamination by flying insects in an innovative way BO	Benefits 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none">ensuring food quality and safety, as well as contributing to the sustainability, health and well-being of consumers BO
KPIs 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none">automation in the control of flying insects BO	Processes to achieve the objective 5 <ul style="list-style-type: none">insect counting and classification insect control BO	
Problems that need to be addressed 6 <ul style="list-style-type: none">inaccuracy in counting and correct identification of insectsdelay in the control process due to manual processes BO		

Expected results: List of possible problems to be addressed with AM solutions in RDI projects

Problem Identification

Purpose: Identify one or more problems to be addressed in the project as an AM solution and the respective problem or opportunity priorities

Tasks of Process 7

- Light traps are installed at the company. The traps have a plate to which the insects stick. A period is established for replacing the plates. The plate is removed, and the number of insects trapped and the type of insect are counted. This information is recorded in a spreadsheet.

BO ED

Why 8

- Helps with pest control by alerting you if there is an infestation that needs to be treated.

BO ED

How it's done 9

- The entire process is carried out manually by a pest controller

BO ED

Stakeholders 10

- Pest controllers are the responsible parties
- Company and end users may be affected.

BO ED

Where 11

- Any place where there is a light trap

BO ED

How often 12

- It is set according to the client's needs, but can be daily, weekly, or monthly. It cannot exceed a monthly limit.

BO ED

Gravity 13

- counting 5
- classification 3

BO

Urgency 14

- counting 5
- classification 5

BO

Tendency to worst 15

- counting 3
- classification 5

BO

Multiplication 16

- counting 75
- classification 75

Data Tasks 13

- automation of the process of counting and classifying insects stuck to the light trap plates

CD

How it helps the customer 14

- The added value for the customer is the accuracy in counting and classifying insects, as well as the agility of this process.

CD

Required data 15

- image of light trap plates

CD

Expected results: Problem breakdown based on 5W2H, list of prioritized problems according to the GUT matrix and identification of possible AM solutions for the analyzed problems

Feasibility Analysis

Purpose: To assess whether the treatment of the problem(s) is feasible to be treated with an AM solution in this project by analyzing aspects of data, solutions and risks.

<p>Priority problem 17</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> quantify and classify insects <p>BO CD</p>	<p>Data input 18</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> images of light trap signs, which can be in any format The images are stored in the non-relational Firebase database <p>BO ED CD</p>	<p>Data quality 19</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of insects Noise-free plate Image quality Focused image <p>BO CD</p>
<p>Data Output 20</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The number of insects on the plates which insects they are will be presented in a trend graph <p>CD</p>		<p>Performance metrics 21</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> have not yet been defined <p>CD</p>
<p>Risks identify the risks inherent to this project with the following characteristics 22</p> <p>Description - Impact - Probability - Contingency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Problem - High - Consider more than one data source Shortage of Staff - Medium - Document everything developed to decentralize knowledge Lack of Computing Resources - Low - Acquire Computing Resources Poor Model Performance - High - Perform tests as quickly as possible and conduct an in-depth literature review <p>BO CD</p>		
<p>Algorithms 23</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yolo <p>CD</p>	<p>References 25</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insect Detection and Classification Based on an Improved Convolutional Neural Network (VGG19) Detection and classification of whiteflies and development stages on soybean leaves images using an improved deep learning strategy <p>CD</p>	
<p>Baseline 24</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> does not have it yet <p>CD</p>		

Expected results: Problems that can be addressed with AM solutions in RDI projects